

FORMATION OF MUSICAL ABILITIES IN EDUCATORS BY MEANS OF MULTIMEDIA PROGRAMS WITH GAMES IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS

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Annotation: this article discusses the issues of preparing pupils of preschool educational organizations for school, giving them knowledge on the basis of innovative ideas.

Keywords: education, regulatory document, educational efficiency, multimedia technology, computers, style, arithmetic operations, environmental impact, presentation, innovation.

The 21st century is a century of technology, and today it is difficult to imagine organizations or institutions that are not equipped with modern computer and information technology tools, including in pre-Matab educational organizations, the tools of modern computer and information technology are used efficiently and appropriately. This not only affects the special approach of educators to their activities, but also has a positive effect on educators. Attracting the attention of children up to school age to something voluntarily causes a lot of difficulty not only in parents, but also in foster educators. In order to attract the attention of the caregivers to one point for a certain period of time and to ensure that it is remembered, playful multimedia comes in handy quite effectively. Children up to school age are given to the game, and it is difficult to concentrate them on one point for more than 10-15 minutes. And through playful multimedia means, in the image of their favorite characters, it is possible to concentrate their attention at one point on the basis of the interaction with them through a virtual educator, and through this, with the help of playful music-didactic multimedia techniques, we can develop rhythmic movements in them, dance and hearing abilities corresponding to the melody. We need to pay special attention to the fact that not every game is suitable for those who are brought up. The goals and objectives of the game multimedia or musical didactic games are [the rules of law], which differ from each other. Before we apply playful multimedia techniques, it is essential that we also take special care of the child's age aspect. It is necessary that any methods applied to children have a positive effect on their development as a mature person, both mental and physical, so that the educator is able to choose a method that is suitable for the children of the educator who are brought up also has a great moral... musical-didactic games are

very effectively used to reveal hidden abilities in This process, which is associated with gaming activity, is able to concentrate on itself the attention of all the children around him, and in this, children become involved in the process of involuntary activity. They begin to distinguish whether it is major(cheerful) or minor(sad)music, first of all,comparing music during the game, realizing the high and low tone of melodies. In the process of activity in its traditional form, it is somewhat difficult for us to grow the musical abilities of educators and instill musical taste in their minds. And through playful and didactic music, the possibilities are even easier for us to bring creative hidden abilities in them to the surface ,to rivalish musical tastes and to shape musical literacy, to grow musical abilities and to develop them in every possible way.

As they reflect on music, it is jioiz to emphasize that the art of music serves as an important tool in the aesthetic education of children. Why say that the art of music is a divine power that leads a person to perfection, calling them only to goodness. In other words, the art of music is considered a bond that connects the hands to the hands and the tongues to the tongues. All the reforms and achievements in the field of musical art will make a worthy contribution to the development of our society and will make the world hearsay of our country. The art of music is the most important form of aesthetic attitude to reality.

The basis of the use of multimedia technology in MTTs is the need to establish the scientific and theoretical foundations of increasing the effectiveness of the educational process using advanced pedagogical and information technologies in this regard, create a methodology and prepare relevant activities with its organization, and introduce them into practice. To do this, it is advisable to identify the peculiarities of the use of multimedia technology in MTTs, take into account the age of children in this process, the character traits inherent in each of them, the intellectual capabilities, abilities and interests of each of their wards, and, based on these, prepare didactic materials, study methods of pedagogical-psychological influence on children in

Based on these urgent tasks, the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. On November 6, 2020,the decree of Mirziyoyev”on measures for the development of educational and educational and scientific fields in the new development period of Uzbekistan " PF-6108 was approved. The decree, together with the Ministry of preschool education, the Ministry of development of Information Technologies and communications, the state inspectorate for quality control of Education and other interested ministries and departments, was set as a task in a separate paragraph on the introduction of modern forms of

teaching, new pedagogical and information technologies in the preschool education system until January 1, 2022¹.

In conclusion, the adoption of such decrees and decisions aimed at ensuring the development of the growing younger generation as a mature, harmonious personality in all respects, the formation of a mentally and physically healthy person testifies to how relevant the topic of the dissertation is.

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